

Pump Beam Shaping for Energy Maximization in Passively Q-switched Nd:YAG-based Microchip Lasers

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Abstract: Pump beam modification improved nanosecond pulse energy in Nd:YAG-based microchip lasers, achieving over fourfold energy increases: up to 420 μJ at 1.06 μm , 135 μJ at 1.34 μm , and 91 μJ at 1.44 μm .

1. Introduction

A passively Q-switched microchip laser (MCL), composed of a bonded active medium and saturable absorber with resonator mirrors directly deposited on the crystal ends, represents a compact and robust source of nanosecond pulses with energies reaching up to the millijoule range [1]. These miniature lasers, utilizing an Nd:YAG active medium, which is well-suited for this design due to its relatively long upper laser level lifetime, have the potential for various applications, such as LIDAR, LIBS, micromachining, and medical treatment, depending on the output pulse energy, duration, and wavelength [2].

The Q-switched pulse energy can be estimated using a relation derived from the rate equations:

$$E = \frac{h\nu A}{2\sigma\gamma} \ln\left(\frac{1}{R}\right) \ln\left(\frac{n_i}{n_f}\right), \quad (1)$$

where $h\nu$ is the laser photon energy, A is the effective beam cross-sectional area, σ is the stimulated emission cross-section, γ is a factor involving the degeneracies of the upper and lower laser levels, R is an output resonator mirror reflectivity, n_i and n_f are the initial and final population inversions, respectively [3]. According to this relation, which is derived under the assumptions of fast Q-switching and the plane-wave approximation, the pulse energy is expected to increase linearly with the effective pumped area. Although this simplified model does not apply to more realistic cases such as Gaussian beams, it still offers a valuable approximation that helps predict the trend of pulse energy with increasing pumped area in practical laser systems.

In this work, we present three longitudinally diode-pumped passively Q-switched microchip lasers with an Nd:YAG active medium, emitting at wavelengths of 1.06, 1.34, and 1.44 μm . For these lasers, we experimentally maximized the output pulse energy by shaping the pump beam using several compact focusing systems [4].

2. Laser parameters and pumping methodology

The parameters of the tested microchip lasers are listed in Table 1. For MCL1, a Cr:YAG saturable absorber was used for Q-switching, while V:YAG absorbers were employed in MCL2 and MCL3. All lasers were pumped by a pulsed laser diode operating at a wavelength of 0.8 μm and a repetition rate of 50 Hz. The diode current and pulse duration were adjusted due to threshold variations introduced by the different pump focusing optics.

Each focusing system with an outer diameter of less than 12.2 mm consisted of the same aspherical collimator with an 8 mm focal length, paired with an aspherical focusing lens of varying focal lengths (ranging from 8.0 to 18.4 mm). By using these different optics, the pump beam waist area could be increased by more than a factor of four, from 0.13 to 0.58 mm^2 , potentially leading to enhanced pulse energy, as suggested by the relation in the previous section.

3. Results and discussion

The dependence of output pulse energy and pulse duration on the pump beam waist area for the tested microchip lasers is shown in Fig. 1. For MCL1 and MCL3, more than a twofold energy increase was observed as the beam waist area increased, with pulse energies rising from 149 to 420 μJ for MCL1 and from 42 to 91 μJ for MCL3,

Table 1. Parameters of the tested MCLs: λ - emission wavelength; c_{at} - Nd^{3+} atomic concentration; d - crystal diameter; l_{AM} - active medium length; l_{SA} - saturable absorber length; T_0 - saturable absorber initial transmission at λ ; R_{OC} - output coupler reflectivity; E_p - pump pulse energy range.

Label	λ [nm]	c_{at} [%]	d [mm]	l_{AM} [mm]	l_{SA} [mm]	T_0 [%]	R_{OC} [%]	E_p [mJ]
MCL1	1064	0.9	5	20	1.8	60	60	13.5 – 31.1
MCL2	1338	1.1	5	4	0.7	85	90	5.2 – 14.8
MCL3	1444	1.2	5	4	1.0	94	94	5.7 – 13.0

respectively. For MCL2, the increase was even greater, exceeding a factor of four, from 32 to 135 μJ . The energy dependence appears approximately linear, which is consistent with the theoretical relation discussed earlier. However, further increases in beam area would likely lead to energy saturation. As expected, higher output pulse energies required higher pump pulse energies.

The pulse duration, on the other hand, was not significantly affected by the pump beam waist area. The average pulse durations were 3.7 ns for MCL1, 1.7 ns for MCL2, and 8.1 ns for MCL3. Correspondingly, the maximum peak powers achieved were 119 kW, 81 kW, and 12 kW, respectively.

Fig. 1. Output parameters of Nd:YAG-based microchip lasers as a function of pump beam waist area, adjusted using different focusing optics: (a) pulse energy, (b) pulse duration (FWHM), and (c) pulse peak power.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we experimentally demonstrated that pump beam shaping is an effective strategy for increasing the output energy of passively Q-switched Nd:YAG microchip lasers. By modifying the focusing optics, the pump beam waist area was increased by a factor of more than four, resulting in significant enhancements in pulse energy. The maximum achieved values were 420 μJ at 1.06 μm , 135 μJ at 1.34 μm , and 91 μJ at 1.44 μm . These results confirm the theoretical prediction that pulse energy scales with the effective pumped area, and highlight the importance of careful pump beam optimization in the design of compact high-energy laser sources. This approach could benefit applications in LIDAR, micromachining, or spectroscopy, where both pulse energy and system compactness are critical.

References

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